

The 'Secret Census' of 1916 and South Australia's Ithacans

A Reflection

Yianni Cartledge & Andrekos Varnava

Earlier this year my supervisor and colleague Prof Andrekos Varnava and I published an article in *Australian Historical Studies (AHS)*, examining the 1916 'secret census' of Greeks in Australia.¹ In the article, we explored the secret census itself, the context of it being recorded, the subsequent accompanying issues for naturalisation, and the census' links both with the rise of anti-Greek sentiment during the 1910s, and with broader policy around migrant monitoring. We also challenged the number of Greeks in Australia during the period. The article took South Australia as a case study, as it was both 'close to home', and a manageable but unique data set.

I would like to acknowledge the support of Prof Andrekos Varnava, Kyriaco Nikias, Zoe Thomaidou, *Australian Historical Studies*, the Australian Migration History Network, and the Ithacan Historical Society.

When referring to 'I' in this paper, we are referring to the thoughts and reflections of Yianni Cartledge; while 'we' refers to both Yianni Cartledge and Andrekos Varnava.

Abbreviations used: NAA = National Archives of Australia; NLA = National Library of Australia.

¹ Yianni Cartledge and Andrekos Varnava, 'Making and Monitoring a 'Suspect Community': Australian Attacks on Greeks and the 'Secret Census' in 1916', *Australian Historical Studies*, 55, no. 3, (2024): 485–505.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1031461X.2023.2293837>

The article was also presented as a conference paper at the Australian Historical Association (AHA) Conference 'Milestones' 2023; the Flinders CHASS PA Winter Conference 2023; and the Greek Orthodox Community of SA (GOCSA) Odyssey Festival 2023.

It also featured as a blogpost for the Australia Migration History Network: Yianni Cartledge and Andrekos Varnava, 'The 'Secret Census' of Greeks in Australia, 1916', *Australian Migration History Network Blog*, 6 October 2023:

<https://amigrationhn.wordpress.com/2023/10/06/the-secret-census-of-greeks-in-australia-1916/>

We paired our own interrogation with discussions by earlier historians, who in many ways laid the groundwork.²

Later that year, a journalist from the Greek Australian newspaper *Neos Kosmos* contacted me about the *AHS* study, proposing to write an article from a more personal perspective, looking at the descendants of those counted, to gain further insight.³ The article published by *Neos Kosmos* provoked an interesting and engaged public debate, which showed a particular curiosity for who was and was not counted by the census-takers in 1916, and the reasons why some known Greeks in Australia were left out.⁴ This is the departure point for this reflection, which will look at what

² Some notable earlier works include: Hugh Gilchrist, *Australians and Greeks, Vol II: The Middle Years* (Halstead Press, 1997), 16–9; Penny Anagnostou, ‘Ethnic Politics: Migrants and Ethnic Organisations’, thesis (Flinders University, 1982); Effy Alexakis and Leonard Janiszewski, *In Their Own Image: Greek Australians* (Hale & Iremonger, 1998), 17; Reginald Appleyard and John N. Yiannakis, *Greek Pioneers in Western Australia* (University of WA Press, 2002), 70–1, 89, 241–2; Andonis Piperoglou, ‘Greek Settlers: Race, Labour and the Making of White Australia, 1890s–1920s’, PhD thesis (La Trobe University, 2016), 141–4; John N. Yiannakis, *Megisti in the Antipodes* (Hesperian Press, 1996).

³ Zoe Thomaidou, ‘Australia’s 1916 ‘Secret Census’: A story of distrust towards Greek migrants’, *Neos Kosmos*, 28 July 2024:

<https://neoskosmos.com/en/2024/07/28/features/did-you-know-of-australias-1916-secret-census-count-of-greeks/>

This included myself, with my great-great-grandfather Ioannis Gronthos, along with his brother, brother-in-law, and nephew, counted at Port Pirie SA (see: Yianni Cartledge, ‘GRONTHOS and SAFOS Families’, in *History of Greeks in Port Pirie: Celebrating 100 Plus Years*, ed. Nick Seindanis, (Greek Community of Port Pirie, 2024), 277. Alongside this, the Ithacan Historical Society’s Vice President Kyriaco Nikias also had ancestors counted, from both Constantinople and Ithaca, and aided me in identifying many of the South Australian Ithacans in the census.

⁴ The *Neos Kosmos* article sparked some public discussion around who and who was not included, with questions being raised by Andrew Raftopoulos who saw some early successful Ithacans as examples of exceptions. See here: Andrew Raftopoulos, ‘Australia’s 1916 Secret Census of Greeks: A commentary’, *Neos Kosmos*, 31 August 2024:

<https://neoskosmos.com/en/2024/08/31/features/australias-1916-secret-census-of-greeks-a-commentary/>

While important and valid, many of the points raised by Raftopoulos were previously discussed in the original *AHS* journal article, which looked at the nuances around

the secret census was, what it meant for Greeks in Australia, and how it was implemented in South Australia as a case study. This includes a brief interrogation of the South Australian data. It will then examine Ithacans in the census, which naturally brings up questions of their role and place in early South Australia. Some final further thoughts will be offered to close this discussion. I hope this shall mark out a useful approach which might be taken up for studying the census data for the other Australian states.

The secret census was carried out by local police, on behalf of the Special Intelligence Bureau, from June 1916, and was Australia-wide (except for the Northern Territory).⁵ It aimed to catalogue every Greek person and their businesses and meeting places. Greeks were recorded covertly, and detailed information, including name, address, gender, age, occupation, means of communication, nature of transport, and distance from capital were collected, as well as rough numbers of Greeks meeting in clubs, cafés, and other meeting places (Appendix 1). These measures were taken in the event that Greeks were to be interned. Despite other ‘secret censuses’ of migrant communities taken during WWI, no other neutral group were recorded to such detail, as most other lists only took the names of men of military age.⁶

The ultimate driving factors behind the secret census stemmed from wartime paranoid and migrant distrust – Greece was neutral during WWI, and King Constantine was leaning sympathetically towards the German position, due to the Kaiser being his brother-in-law. There was also a recent

recording. A clarifying reply can be read here: Yianni Cartledge and Andrekos Varnava, ‘The 1916 ‘secret census’ of Greeks in Australia: Reclarifying some misconceptions’, *Neos Kosmos*, 9 September 2024:

<https://neoskopos.com/en/2024/09/09/news/community/the-1916-secret-census-of-greeks-in-australia-reclarifying-some-misconceptions/>

⁵ A separate count was taken in November 1916 in the NT, of both Greek and Maltese military-aged men.

⁶ Other lists included: all foreign passengers inward and outward from Darwin in 1915–16; Italians in 1917–18; military-age French men in 1918; Turks in 1918; Russians, Russo-Poles, Russo-Finns and Finns in Victoria in 1919; Bulgarians in 1920; Czechs and Slovaks in 1920–21; Austrians and Hungarians in 1920–21; Yugoslavs in 1921; Swiss in NSW in 1921; and Dutch in 1922–25. See: NAA/A385/1–6, 14–20. This is compared to the monitoring of Greeks in 1916 recorded in NAA/A385, 7–13.

history of racial attacks on Greek migrants, stemming from both questions of loyalty, and the growing trend of ‘White labourism’. The secret census was essentially a sequel to an earlier step in November 1915, when the Australian government had categorised Greeks as ‘enemy aliens’ for the purposes of naturalisation, only considering applications from those aged 60 and above. Through these two measures, Greeks were actively discriminated against, even though Greece was not an ‘enemy’ country. This led the Greeks to be viewed and monitored as a ‘suspect community’, a key theoretical framing employed in our study.⁷

The numbers

Overall, 2,662 Greeks were counted during the secret census (and including a subsequent count of military-aged Greek men in the Northern Territory) (Table 1). In South Australia, 178 Greeks were recorded in the ‘secret census’, including only 14 females and 4 children. Although South Australia’s numbers were trumped by the much larger New South Wales (900), Queensland (567), Victoria (461), and even Western Australia (285), it forms an important case study due its small sample size, manageable dataset, and tightknit community that thrived on chain migration.⁸ The South Australian Greek community is also an under-researched diaspora in general, especially pre-WWII, when compared to the larger and vibrant

⁷ See, for comparison: Evan Smith and Andrekos Varnava, ‘Creating a “Suspect Community”: Monitoring and Controlling the Cypriot Community in Inter-War London’, *The English Historical Review*, 132, no. 558 (2017): 1149–81; Andrekos Varnava, Marinella Marmo and Evan Smith, ‘Border Control and Undesirables in Britain and Australia’, *Immigrants & Minorities*, 40, nos 1–2, (2022): 1–12; Evan Smith, ‘Shifting Undesirability: Italian Migration, Political Activism and the Australian Authorities from the 1920s to the 1950s’, *Immigrants & Minorities*, 40, nos (1–2) (2022): 106–31; Andrekos Varnava, ‘Border Control and Monitoring “Undesirable” Cypriots in the UK and Australia, 1945–1959’, *Immigrants & Minorities*, 40, nos (1–2) (2022): 132–76.

⁸ Chain migration refers to migrants from particular locations and social groups following their compatriots to other places. See the work of John S. MacDonald and Leatrice D. MacDonald, ‘Chain Migration Ethnic Neighborhood Formation and Social Networks’, *Milbank Memorial Fund Quarterly*, 42, no. 1, (1964), 82–97.

eastern state communities.⁹

Table 1: Number of Greeks listed in the 1916 secret census and in the Northern Territory.¹⁰

State	Total
Victoria ¹¹	461
Queensland	567
New South Wales	900
South Australia	178
Western Australia ¹²	285
Tasmania	7
Total (without NT)	2,398
Northern Territory (Gilchrist Estimate)	120–350
Northern Territory (Alien Registrations 1916–17)	~264
Total (with NT)	2,662

⁹ See: Michael P. Tsounis, ‘Greek Communities in Australia’, PhD thesis (Adelaide University, 1971); Michael P. Tsounis, ‘Greeks in South Australia’, thesis (Adelaide University, 1963); Michael P. Tsounis, *The Story of a Community: A short pictorial history of the Greek Orthodox Community of South Australia* (GOCSA, 1991); *Λεύκωμα: 60 Years of Service to the Community, 1930–1990* (GOCSA, 1990); Athan N. Anagnostou and Penny Anagnostou eds., *Our Journey at a Glance: 1930–2010* (GOCSA, 2011); Nick Seindanis, *History of Greeks in Port Pirie: Celebrating 100 Plus Years* (Greek Community of Port Pirie, 2024); Yianni Cartledge, ‘Greek Islander Migration to South Australia 1919–1939: Emigration, Settlement and Community Building’, in Caroline Adams and Brian Dickey (eds.), *South Australia 1919–1939: Essays from the Professional Historians Association (SA)* (PHA SA, 2022), 175–96; Yianni Cartledge (updated by), Nicholas Ganzis (original), ‘Greeks’, *The Wakefield Companion to South Australian History: Second Edition* (Wakefield Press, forthcoming 2024).

¹⁰ See: Greeks–Victoria–Particulars of, 1916–20: NAA/A385/12/65708; Greeks, Queensland, Particulars of, 1916: NAA/A385/9/65704; Return of Greek Residents, New South Wales, 1916: NAA/A385/7/65703; Greeks, SA, Resident in Metropolitan Police Division, 1916: NAA/A385/10B/ 65706; Greeks, WA, Particulars of, 1916: NAA/A385/13/65709; Greeks, Tasmania, Particulars of, 1916: NAA/A385/11/65707.

¹¹ The Victoria number is uncertain, due to multiple versions held by the NAA and Gilchrist. See: Papers of Hugh Gilchrist, ‘The Secret Census of Greeks in Australia, 1916’, NLA: MS 4931, 1827–2007; Greeks, Victoria, Particulars of, 1916–20, NAA/A385/12/65708.

¹² Some estimate as high as 1,000 in WA in 1916. See: NAA/A11803/1914/89/150.

What the South Australian case study ultimately unveils is that there was a strong islander presence in South Australia, most of whom were labourers.¹³ There were also two burgeoning communities, centred on Port Pirie and Adelaide's CBD (Table 2). Of the 115 Greeks counted in Port Pirie (by far the larger Greek centre in this period), 101 were labourers working at the BHP Smelters. A further 6 were fishermen, 5 restaurant workers, 1 hawker, 1 wharfie, and 1 listed as 'old age' (Table 3). This displayed Port Pirie as an overwhelmingly labouring and male community.

Adelaide CBD and surrounds, which hosted 47 Greeks, had a more diverse range of professions (Table 3). This included café and other hospitality and retail workers (tobacconists, fish shops, and restaurants), labourers, cooks, fish hawkers, a watchmaker, a confectioner, and women listed as 'home duties.' This diversity can be put down to both the cosmopolitanism of city life, as well as the industry differences between Adelaide and Port Pirie. The Port Adelaide region, which had 12 Greeks, similarly had a mix of restaurant workers, fishermen, labourers, and retirees.

There were 18 businesses recorded in South Australia that were either owned by Greeks or considered meeting places for Greeks. 11 of these were in the Adelaide CBD, 5 in Port Pirie (despite the larger Greek community being there), 1 in Gawler and 1 in Port Adelaide. The majority (11) were fish and oyster shops of various kinds (from take-aways to restaurants), while 3 were restaurants, 1 a café, 1 confectionery store, 1 tailor, and 1 general store. Hindley Street, Adelaide hosted 4 of the fish shops, while Florence St, Port Pirie, hosted 2 restaurants and a fish shop. Many of these establishments between the 1910s-20s formed case studies for the exploration of early Adelaide eateries in Thompson and Smith's *Traces: Where Adelaide Ate Out 1836–1960*.¹⁴

¹³ Identifying islanders was not an onerous task, as they were mainly deduced by their often unique surnames. Additionally, many individuals were already known via previous research, or by finding naturalisation records in the years following.

¹⁴ Darryl J. Thompson and James S. Smith, *Traces: Where Adelaide Ate Out 1836–1960* (James S. Smith & Associates, 2015), 753–74.

Table 2: Number of Greeks in South Australia by location, 1916.¹⁵

Port Pirie and surrounds (including Ellendale and Port Pirie West)	115
Adelaide CBD and surrounds (including Hyde Park, Unley, Norwood, & Prospect)	47
Port Adelaide and surrounds (including Glanville, Peterhead, Rosewater, Dockville, and Graytown)	12
Port Wakefield	2
Gawler	1
Kadina	1
Total	178

Table 3: Professions of Greeks in South Australia, 1916.

Smelter	101
Restaurant	18
Fisherman	10
Home duties	10
Cook	8
Labourer	7
Café	5
Fish hawker/fishmonger	3
Fish shop	3
Retired	3
Tobacconist	2
Master Mariner	1
Confectioner	1
Foreman	1
Hawker	1
N/A	1
Shop assistant	1
Watchmaker	1
Wharf labourer	1
Total	178

¹⁵ Greek – South Australia – Greeks Resident in Metropolitan Police Division, 1916: NAA/A385/10B/65706; Greek – South Australia – Particulars of, 1916: NAA/A385/10A/65705; Papers of Hugh Gilchrist, ‘The Secret Census of Greeks in Australia, 1916’, NLA: MS 4931, 1827–2007.

There are some unusual recordings (and lack of recordings), that bring up provocative questions of class, religion, assimilation, ‘whiteness’, and who was Greek. For instance, the South Australian list records some non-Greeks, who were ‘lumped together’ with the Greeks being counted, including two Syrian (or Lebanese) men, a Persian man, and three ‘Christian Turks’. Were these men included due to religion? Language? Birthplace (i.e. Ottoman Empire or proximity)? Or even just for being associated with Greek communities, or for being ‘confused’ with Greeks by those counting them? The reasons remain unclear.

The definition of ‘Greek’ itself appeared fluid, and better described as ‘Greek speakers’, with many being counted despite the various nationalities they held. These included Ottoman, Italian (via the Italian Dodecanese), British (via Cyprus and Egypt), as well as being from places with historic and recent autonomy and independence (such as Crete, Samos, and Ikaria), and with recent history as part of foreign empires (such as the Ionian Islands being British during much of the nineteenth century).¹⁶

Comparatively, two landowning pastoralist families of Greek origins, the Norths (an anglicisation of Tramountanas) and the Rallis, were both omitted, despite being prominent Greek Australians during the period.¹⁷

¹⁶ Cartledge and Varnava, ‘Making and Monitoring a ‘Suspect Community’’, 490.

¹⁷ See on the Norths: Penny Anagnostou, ‘Greeks in South Australia’, in *The Australian People: An Encyclopedia of the Nation, Its People and Their Origins* ed. James Jupp (Cambridge University Press, 2001), 401; Hugh Gilchrist, *Australians and Greeks, Vol. I: The Early Years* (Halstead Press, 1992), 73–5 & 117; George Kanarakis, *In the Wake of Odysseus: Portraits of Greek Settlers in Australia* (RMIT University Publishing, 1997), 15–24.

See on the Rallis: Balaklava Centenary Book Committee, *Balaklava – Change and Challenge: A History of Balaklava and Surrounding Districts* (Griffin Press, 1977), 2–3 & 13–5; G.S. Kempe, *The Shropshire Sheep: With a description of Mr. Stephen S. Ralli’s Flock at Werocata, S.A.* (J.H. Sherring & Co., 1897); Timotheos Catsiyannis, *Pandias Stephen Rallis, 1793–1865: The Founder of the Greek Community in London* (1986); Timotheos Catsiyannis, *The Greek Community of London* (1993); Alexander Pantia Ralli and Alexander Antonio Ralli, *A Pedigree of the Rallis of Scio, 1700–1892* (1896); Yianni Cartledge, ‘Stephen S. Ralli of Balaklava: Anglo-Greek Migrants in SA’, in *Amateurs, Academics and Archivists: 20 years of the History Council of South Australia* (Wakefield Press, forthcoming 2024). On the Chios Massacre, spurring on the Chiot diaspora in Britain (which includes the Ralli family) see: Yianni Cartledge, ‘The Chios Massacre and

Their absence in the record triggers many further questions. Were they omitted due to class? As agriculturalists, were they ‘valued’ more than small business owners and labourers? Was it due to them being more ‘assimilated’ than other Greeks? Was it due to religion (the Norths had converted to Catholicism, and the Rallis bounced between Anglicanism and Orthodoxy)? Was it due to birthplace? The North children and grandchildren were born in South Australia, and the Rallis were born in the UK and South Australia. Did they simply ‘hide’ their Greekness due to the era’s anti-Greek sentiments? It certainly was not to do with anglicisation of names, or naturalisation, as other anglicised and naturalised Greeks were counted. Another man, Port Pirie’s first Greek, Miltiadis Dimitrios Bidzanis (who used the name Michael De Diar) of Kytheran and Cretan origins, who became a successful trader, boat owner, and master mariner, was similarly absent from the secret census.¹⁸ Ultimately, the secret census appeared to be taken in an inconsistent way, that had shifting criteria for who and who was not included.

Ithacans in South Australia’s ‘secret census’

While many of these questions may never be answered, we can better appreciate the working of the census and what it tells us about Australia’s early Greeks by focussing on subgroups among those counted. Greeks who shared an origin in a particular place, usually islanders, formed tight-knit

Chiot Emigration: A Coerced Diaspora’, in Yianni Cartledge and Andrekos Varnava (eds.), *New Perspectives on the Greek War of Independence: Myths, Realities, Legacies and Reflections* (Palgrave Macmillan/Springer Nature, 2022), 217–41; Yianni Cartledge, ‘Chiot Refugees in the British Empire after the Chios Massacre (1822)’, in Andrekos Varnava, Yianni Cartledge and Evan Smith (eds.), *Forced Migration: Exiles and Refugees in the UK and the British Empire, 1810s-1940s* (Brill, forthcoming 2025); Yianni Cartledge, ‘The Chios Massacre (1822) and early British Christian-humanitarianism’, *Historical Research*, 93(259), February 2020, 52–72:

<https://doi.org/10.1093/hisres/htz004>

¹⁸ See also: Seindanis, *History of Greeks in Port Pirie*, 1–2; George Kanarakis, ‘Miltiades Bidzanis/Bidzanakis – Michael De Diar’, *Kythera Family.net*, 1 January 2006:

<https://www.kythera-family.net/en/people/notable-kytherians/miltiades-bidzanisbidzanakis-michael-de-diar>

communities and their network of relations in Australia can be traced through the census. In the research which formed the basis of my doctoral thesis, I looked closely at the secret census to find Ikarians Australia-wide.¹⁹ What I had not done at the time, due to the nature of the project, was to try and place many of the other Greeks (especially islanders) more broadly. Many often had somewhat ‘easily identifiable’ regional surnames and had chain migrated (like the Ikarians of my case study), allowing groups to be identified. When examining the census further, these clusters of compatriots really do stand out, and can offer a window into who was migrating, how they migrated, where they settled, and how they built early communities. This 1910s wave of Greek migrants ultimately can be seen as setting the migratory groundwork that enabled later migrations, such as the interwar and postwar migrant waves.

Another prominent group of early Greek migrants in Australia were those from Ithaca (alongside those from Castellorizo, Kythera, Chios, Ikaria, and Asia Minor). In South Australia, a distinct Ithacan diaspora was beginning to develop, with at least 15 Ithacans identifiable state-wide (as well as two other Ionians), although these clusters were not as large a community as their Aegean and Asia Minor counterparts during the period (Appendix 2).²⁰ It can be concluded, though, that these early Ithacans set the migratory groundwork that was utilised by the Ithacan migrants over the 1920s-30s, and beyond. No doubt, much larger Ithacan communities existed in other states, particularly Victoria and New South Wales, where they similarly balanced labouring with hospitality, and established long-lasting centres of community.²¹ These communities and their

¹⁹ Yianni Cartledge, ‘Aegean Islander Migration to the United Kingdom and Australia, 1815–1945: Emigration, Settlement, Community Building, and Integration’, PhD thesis (Flinders University, 2024), 282–4.

²⁰ For the identification of Ithacan surnames, see the useful index in George Paxinos, *Passage to Ithaca: History – Surnames – Identity*, 2nd edn. (Ithacan Historical Society, 2022), 142–217.

²¹ See George Paxinos, *The Ithacans: The Ithacan Philanthropic Society*, Melbourne, 1916–2016 (Ithacan Historical Society, 2016), 55–8; Georgia Charpantidou, *The Embodiment of a Distant Homeland: The history of the Greek Orthodox Community of*

demographics as per the secret census certainly contain merit for further study.

Although very small-scale, some interesting understandings emerge from the secret census on who the early Ithacans and their two Ionian counterparts were in South Australia. There seemed to be a somewhat even split in settlement between the Adelaide CBD, Port Adelaide, and Port Pirie (Table 4). House sharing was not as evident as it was for other Greeks, like the many Aegean and Asia Minor migrants working at the BHP Smelters, who often dwelt together. Although, three men, Chris Callinicos, Nicholas Callinicos, and Alec Paizis, appeared to be living together at Commercial Rd, Port Adelaide – it is known they were all close relatives.²² Much like the other Greeks in South Australia at the time, the Ithacans were male dominated, and the average age was 31. There was only 1 woman listed, Annie Morris, wife of Dennis Morris (Moraitis), fish shop proprietor of Hindley St. Additionally, an even split between professional fields was demonstrated, with 7 in labouring jobs and 7 in hospitality (Table 5). The Morris and Callinicos surnames were the only with multiple members in the state, although no doubt there were familial or social connections between many of the others (Table 6). For instance, another Ithacan, Charalambos (Bob) Carrangis, husband of Emilia Callinicos (neither were listed in the secret census), would eventually run Carr's Café on Gawler Place. In all, the South Australian Ithacans were the beginnings of the state's diaspora, with strong links between both working-class labouring and the hospitality/enterprising sectors.

In their study of Adelaide's early eateries, Thompson and Smith included the Ithacan-owned Morris (Moraitis) Bros' Fish Café, 38 Hindley St; Comino Café, 21 Hindley St; Carr's (Carrangis) Café, 57 Gawler Place; and the National Café (Callinicos brothers) 52 King William St and later 134a Rundle St, which corroborates the secret census' records.²³ This

Melbourne and Victoria from its founding to 1972, Petro Alexiou (trans.) (Themelio, 2022).

²² Personal correspondence with Kyriaco Nikias, June-September 2024.

²³ Thompson and Smith, *Traces*, 753–74; Effy Alexakis and Leonard Janiszewski, *Greek Cafés and Milk Bars of Australia* (Halstead Press, 2016).

cluster of businesses also demonstrates the significance of Ithacans in the Adelaide CBD's early restaurant scene.

Table 4: Number of Ithacans in South Australia by location, 1916.

Adelaide CBD and surrounds (including Unley)	6
Port Pirie and surrounds (including Port Pirie West)	5
Port Adelaide and surrounds	3
Port Wakefield	1
Total	15

Table 5: Professions of Ithacans in South Australia, 1916.

Smelter	4
Restaurant	3
Fisherman ²⁴	3
Cook	2
Confectioner	1
Fish shop	1
Home duties	1
Total	15

Table 6: Surnames of Ithacans in South Australia, 1916.

Moraitis (<i>Morris</i>)	4
Callinicos	3
Black (possibly <i>Mavros/ Mavrokephalos</i>)	1
Carrangis (<i>Carr</i>)	1
Karatzis	1
Maroudis/Maroudas	1
Paizis	1
Paxinos	1
Paxos (possibly <i>Paxinos</i>)	1
Zambelis	1
Total	15

²⁴ Although, 1 was 'out of work'.

Further thoughts

The secret census ultimately paints a picture of Australia's early Greek community as tightknit, growing, overly male, and heavily labouring. In many ways it gives a broader and rawer snapshot of the nature and demographics of the diaspora until 1916, and can be comparable to early documents like *Life in Australia*, also published 1916.²⁵ However, unlike the other early catalogues from the time, the secret census lacks an east-coast bias, thus giving useful data for other states, such as South Australia (as seen here) and Western Australia.

The key conclusions from the South Australian case are the rural-urban divide, the complex questions of identity and inclusivity it raised, as well as the overwhelming dominance of islanders and labourers. Port Pirie being the centre of the early Greek community, as opposed to Adelaide, is also unique, as other states did not boast larger numbers outside their capital. Port Pirie's organised Greek community would ultimately form in 1924 – being founded 6 years before Adelaide's.²⁶ The Ithacans themselves are a more unique component, as opposed to the Aegean islanders explored in my own earlier research, and the Asia Minor Greeks.²⁷ This is especially seen in their professions, having a balance between labouring and hospitality, which likely echoes their entrepreneurship in other states as well.

Essentially, the secret census is one of the clearest records of the early Greek-speaking diasporas of Australia, and a useful tool for interrogation, examination, contextualisation, and extrapolation. I believe the incorporation of the census data into studies of this early period is urgent, and in this age of information sharing, it can be utilised in vastly different ways to build our understanding of these pioneering communities, who are often overlooked in broader accounts of Greek migration to Australia.

²⁵ Ioannis D. Kominos (John D. Comino), *Η Ζωή εν Αυστραλία* [*Life in Australia*], with Georgios Kentavros, Kosmas Andronikos and Emmanouil Andronikos (Australia (Afstralias) Press, 1916).

²⁶ See: Seindanis, *History of Greeks in Port Pirie*.

²⁷ Cartledge, 'Aegean Islander Migration', 282–4; Cartledge and Varnava, 'Making and Monitoring a "Suspect Community"', 485–505.

While small, the early Greek communities captured by the census of 1916 led the way for later Greek migrants by establishing settlement patterns in the new country and marking paths to finding work.²⁸ By focussing on particular subgroups, like Ithacans in South Australia, we can show how these networks formed in some detail.

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²⁸ See: Cartledge, 'Greek Islander Migration to South Australia 1919–1939', 175–96; Yianni Cartledge, 'Beyond the 'Red Rock': The Ikarian Revolution (1912), political radicalism, and the Ikarian diaspora', *Labor History*, November 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0023656X.2024.2428681>.

Appendix 1: Instructions for the ‘secret census’ sent to police departments.²⁹

SECRET. Not to be entered in ordinary official records.

POLICE DEPARTMENT.
INSPECTOR GENERAL’S OFFICE.
SYDNEY
10th June, 1916.

Please arrange for steps to be at once taken to quietly and not confidentially summarise all particulars relating to Greeks resident in New South Wales.

As far as possible personal particulars should be furnished as to each individual. Where, however, this is impracticable owing to the numbers or other difficulties, particulars should be furnished of approximately the numbers of any colonies of Greeks, the locality, means of communication whether rail, ship, or coach, and distances from Sydney.

With regard to cafes, clubs, or recognised centres where Greeks congregate, the names of the proprietors, managers, nature etc of such clubs should be obtained and a close watch kept upon these establishments without in any way attracting attention or exciting suspicion.

Personal particulars of individual Greeks can be furnished in the form set out hereunder marked “A”.

Particulars of Clubs, cafes, colonies, or centres where Greeks are known to congregate can be set out in the form marked “B” hereunder. Sufficient copies of this circular memo are being forwarded to Superintendents in charge of Districts to allow of one copy being sent to Inspectors in charge of a Division or Sub-District, or Sergeant in charge.

The utmost expedition must be used in the preparation of the forms. In Divisions or Sub-Districts where no Greeks reside, the Officer in charge should furnish promptly a Nil return, and keep close observation

²⁹ NAA/A385/8/65702, form received by James Mitchell, Inspector General of Police, Sydney, 10 June 1916.

on any influx of persons of Greek nationality after such Nil return has been furnished.

The returns when complete must be forwarded by the District Superintendents to this office marked "SECRET AND CONFIDENTIAL".

Form "A".

Return of Greeks resident in the _____ District.

Locality or address.	Name of person. (Surname to be placed first.)	Sex	Age. Approximate.	Occupation.	Means of communication. Nature of transport. Rail, ship, coach, etc.	Distance from Sydney.

Form "B".

Locality	Means of communication. Nature of transport. Rail, ship, coach, etc.	Distance from Sydney.	Club, cafe, or other institution.	Number of persons.	Remarks.
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Appendix 2: Ithacans (and other Ionians) in the 1916 'secret census'.

Town/ Suburb	Address	Surname	First name	Gender	Age	Occupation
Unley	Unley Rd, Unley	Morris (<i>Moraitis</i>)	Dennis	M	36	Fish shop proprietor
Unley	Unley Rd, Unley	Morris (<i>Moraitis</i>)	Annie	F	35	Home duties
Adelaide	27 Robert St, Adelaide	Carrangis (<i>Carr</i>)	John	M	58	Confectioner
Adelaide	21 Hindley St, Adelaide	Zambelis ¹	Kiminos (<i>Kimon</i>)	M	33	Cook
Adelaide	256 Franklin St, Adelaide	Morris (<i>Moraitis</i>)	Dimos	M	20	Cook
Adelaide	55 Hindley St, Adelaide	Morris (<i>Moraitis</i>)	Nicholas	M	34	Restaurant proprietor
Port Wakefield	Port Wakefield	Black (<i>Mavros/ Mavrokephalos</i>)	John	M	60	Fisherman
Port Adelaide	Commercial Rd, Port Adelaide	Callinicos	Chris	M	24	Restaurant keeper
Port Adelaide	Commercial Rd, Port Adelaide	Callinicos	Nicholas	M	20	Restaurant assistant
Port Adelaide	Commercial Rd, Port Adelaide	Paizis	Alec	M	29	Out of businesses, ex fisherman

This table is a transcription from the 'secret census' although amended for readability and clarity. The amendments include the spelling of names and other grammatical issues. Names in brackets are alternative surnames and first names (either their Greek surnames/first names, or the names they were known by).

¹ Zambelis is possibly an Ithacan, but could be a Lefkadian.

Port Pirie West	2nd St, Island, Port Pirie West	Paxinos	Nicholas	M	20	Smelter
Port Pirie	George St, Port Pirie	Karatzis (<i>Karagis</i>)	Dimitrios	M	30	Fisherman
Port Pirie	Affords Rooms, Ellen St, Port Pirie	Maroudis (<i>Maroudas</i>)	Dimitrios	M	20	Smelter
Port Pirie West	Embankment Rd, Port Pirie West	Paxos ²	Stamatis	M	30	Smelter
Port Pirie West	2nd St, Island, Port Pirie West	Callinicos	Christostis (<i>Chrisostom</i>)	M	19	Smelter
Dockville (now Port Adelaide)	Bedford St, Dockville	George (<i>Veslich</i>)	David Dimitrios ³	M	58	Foreman
Glanville	Carlisle St, Glanville	Siffoli	Andrew ⁴	M	98	Old age pensioner

*

² Possibly *Paxinos*.

³ David Dimitrios George (*Veslich*) was from Kythera or Crete.

⁴ Andrew Siffoli was from Kefalonia.

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Abstract

This reflection explores the 1916 ‘secret census’ of Greeks in South Australia — a unique event in the history of migrant monitoring which included the cataloguing of every Greek in Australia by local police on behalf of the Special Intelligence Bureau. The census was conducted due to questions of loyalty during WWI, despite Greece being a neutral country at this point. However, it was no doubt imbued with anti-migrant and xenophobic sentiments. This paper takes South Australia as a case study, and in particular, the small Ithacan community that existed and can be analysed through the rich ‘secret census’ data.

Περίληψη

*Η «Μυστική Απογραφή» του 1916 και οι Ιθακήσιοι της Νότιας
Αυστραλίας: Παρατηρήσεις*

Αυτή η ανακοίνωση διερευνά τη «μυστική απογραφή» των Ελλήνων της Νότιας Αυστραλίας το 1916 — ένα μοναδικό γεγονός στην ιστορία της παρακολούθησης των μεταναστών, το οποίο περιελάμβανε την καταγραφή κάθε Έλληνα στην Αυστραλία από την τοπική αστυνομία για λογαριασμό του Ειδικού Γραφείου Πληροφοριών. Η απογραφή πραγματοποιήθηκε λόγω αμφιβολιών αφοσίωσης κατά τη διάρκεια του Α΄ Παγκοσμίου Πολέμου, παρά το γεγονός ότι η Ελλάδα ήταν ουδέτερη χώρα σε αυτό το σημείο. Ωστόσο, ήταν αναμφίβολα διαποτισμένη από αντιμεταναστευτικά και ξενοφοβικά αισθήματα. Η παρούσα εργασία λαμβάνει ως μελέτη περίπτωσης τη Νότια Αυστραλία και ειδικότερα τη μικρή ιθακήσια κοινότητα που υπήρχε και μπορεί να αναλυθεί μέσα από τα πλούσια δεδομένα της «μυστικής απογραφής».